

SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION AND ANTIBACTERIAL STUDY OF N-[3-(2-CHLOROPHENYL)-1-PHENYLPROPAN-1-ONE]THIOUREA & N-[3-(4-METHOXYPHENYL)-1-PHENYLPROPAN-1-ONE]SEMI CARBAZIDE

Gary Christo C, Abhijith K M, Ramya V*

PG and Research Department of Chemistry,

Kongunadu Arts and Science College, Coimbatore 641029, Tamilnadu, India

Abstract: Mannich reaction is a useful method for the preparation of β -amino carbonyl compounds, which are useful intermediates for the preparation of β -aminoacids. The Mannich reaction is an example of nucleophilic addition of an amine to a carbonyl group followed by dehydration to the Mannich base. Development of an efficient method for the preparation of β -amino carbonyl compounds is thus highly desired. To achieve our objective, we identified the following Mannich bases as core entries and they have been subjected to variety of chemical reaction under different conditions. In this work we synthesized and characterized N-[3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one]thiourea (**1**) & N-[3-(2-chlorophenyl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one]semicarbazide (**2**). The synthesized compounds were characterized by FT-IR, ^1H NMR and Mass techniques.

Keywords: Mannich bases, β -aminoacids, β -amino carbonyl and nucleophilic addition.

Introduction

Mannich in 1912 reported first “Mannich base”, in which two chemical moieties formed linkage by means of methylene bridge ($-\text{CH}_2$)¹. The Mannich bases have played a vital role in the development of synthetic organic chemistry due to the versatile reactivity of these compounds. They are very reactive, useful intermediates of synthetic chemistry and can easily be transformed into variety of new compounds²⁻³. The “Mannich reaction” is the nucleophilic addition reaction of non-enolizable aldehyde (mostly formaldehyde) and an amine (primary, secondary or ammonia) to form resonance stabilized imine (iminium ion or imine salt) and then allowed to react with the substrate involving active hydrogen containing any enolizable carbonyl compound, nitriles, amide, carbamate, electron rich heterocycles [such as furan, pyrrole and thiophene or urea]. Indole is an active substrate; the reaction provides gramine derivatives⁴⁻⁶. Mannich reaction is one of the most important carbon-carbon bond formation reactions inorganic synthesis⁷⁻⁸ and

very useful compounds as building blocks in the synthesis of pharmaceuticals and natural products⁹⁻¹⁰. With their advantages of atom efficient transformations, readily available materials and various products, multicomponent reactions (MCRs) have received significant research interest from chemical and medicinal communities^{11,12}. Multicomponent reactions (MCRs) constitute a major part in the present day organic synthesis with advantages ranging from lower reaction times, increased reaction rates to higher yields and reproducibility. The diversity, efficiency and rapid access to small and highly functionalized organic molecules make this approach of central current interest in the construction of combinatorial libraries and optimization in drug discovery process¹³.

Mannich bases also act as important pharmacophores or bioactive leads which are further used for synthesis of various potential agents of high medicinal value which possess aminoalkyl chain. The examples of clinically useful Mannich bases which consist of aminoalkyl chain are cocaine, fluoxetine, atropine, ethacrynic acid, trihexyphenidyl, procyclidine, ranitidine, biperiden¹⁴⁻¹⁶, and so forth. Mannich bases are known to play a vital role in the development of synthetic pharmaceutical chemistry. The literature studies revealed that Mannich bases are very reactive and can be easily converted to other compounds, for example, reduced to form physiologically active amino alcohols¹⁷. Mannich bases are known to possess potent activities like anti-inflammatory^{18,19}, anticancer^{20,21}, antifilarial²², antibacterial^{23,24}, antifungal^{25,26}, anticonvulsant²⁷, anthelmintic²⁸, antitubercular²⁹, analgesic³⁰ and so forth. Mannich bases and their derivatives are intermediates for the synthesis of bioactive molecules³¹. Mannich bases have gained importance due to their application in antibacterial activity and other applications are in agrochemicals such as plant growth regulators. This manuscript explains in detail the synthesis and characterization of some mannich bases derived from thiourea and semicarbazide.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Melting points were determined on a Boetius micro heating table or on a Raga heating block and are uncorrected. Thin Layer Chromatography [TLC] was performed using glass plates coated with silica gel G [incorporating CaSO₄ (13%) as binder]. Petroleum ether and ethyl acetate were used as irrigant. Spots were visualized with iodine. Purification of the crude samples was carried out using chromatographic columns

packed with silica gel (60-120 mesh). IR Spectra were recorded on Shimadzu FT IR 8201(PC)S spectrometer model spectrometer, using KBR disc method and the absorption frequencies quoted in reciprocal centimeters (cm^{-1}). $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra were taken on BRUKER-400 (400 MHz), BRUKER-500 (500 MHz) spectrometer using trimethylsilane (TMS) as internal reference. The chemical shifts are quoted in parts per million (ppm) (s=singlet; d=doublet; t=triplet; q=quardret; bs=broad singlet and m=multiplet).

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Preparation of N-[3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one]thiourea(1)

N-[3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one]thiourea (1) was prepared by taking 2.8g of thiourea mixed with 4.8ml of acetophenone and stirred well for 30 minutes by using a magnetic stirrer then cool in an ice bath. Then 5.2ml of anisaldehyde was added dropwise with constant stirring. A white precipitate was formed and kept in ice bath for 15minutes. (Scheme-1).

The precipitate was washed well with water several times and purified with a dilute solution of sodiumbisulphite (NaHSO_3) followed by sodiumbicarbonate (NaHCO_3). Then it was washed with water and dried over anhydrous calcium chloride. Evaporation of the excess solvent yield a crude product and chromatographed over a silica gel and eluted with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate mixture (80:20) to obtain the title compound.

1

Scheme-1

Preparation of N-[3-(2-chlorophenyl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one]semicarbazide (2)

N-[3-(2-chlorophenyl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one]semicarbazide (2) was prepared by taking 2.8g of semicarbazide mixed with 4.8ml of acetophenone and stirred well for 30 minutes by using a magnetic stirrer then cool in an ice bath. Then 5.6ml of 2-chlorobenzaldehyde was added dropwise with constant stirring. A white precipitate was formed and kept in ice bath for 15 minutes (**Scheme-2**). The precipitate was washed well with water several times and purified with a dilute solution of sodium bisulphite (NaHSO_3) followed by sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO_3). Then it was washed with water and dried over anhydrous calcium chloride. A pure white powder was obtained by chromatographed over a silica gel and eluted with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate mixture (80:20). TLC method was conducted to check whether the reaction was complete.

Scheme-2

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Synthesis of N-[3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one]thiourea (1)

Thiourea was treated with acetophenone followed by anisaldehyde appeared as white crystalline solid. The IR Spectrum of the compound N-[3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one]thiourea (1) exhibited five strong absorption bands at 3371.57 cm^{-1} & 3263.56 cm^{-1} , 1604.77 cm^{-1} , 1257.59 cm^{-1} and 1080.14 cm^{-1} characteristic of two N-H, C=O, C-O and C=S respectively. In the $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectrum the appearance of peak at $\delta 8.568\text{ ppm}$ was due to $-\text{NH}_2$. The nine aromatic protons ($\text{C}_2\text{-H}$, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}$, $\text{C}_4\text{-H}$, $\text{C}_5\text{-H}$, $\text{C}_6\text{-H}$, $\text{C}_3'\text{-H}$, $\text{C}_4'\text{-H}$, $\text{C}_5'\text{-H}$, $\text{C}_6'\text{-H}$) appeared as a multiplet in the $\delta(6.943\text{-}7.971\text{ ppm})$.

C₃ aliphatic protons appeared as a multiplet at δ 4.492ppm and C₂ aliphatic protons appeared as a doublet δ 3.231ppm. The mass spectrum showed the molecular ion peak at m/z (314). Elemental analysis provided the carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen composition which agreed with the calculated value. Thus the molecular formula of (1) is C₁₇H₁₈N₂O₂S. On the basis of above spectral and elemental details the structure of the compound established as N-[3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one]thiourea (1).

N-[3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one]thiourea (1)

Synthesis of N-[3-(2-chlorophenyl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one]semicarbazide (2)

Semicarbazide was treated with acetophenone followed by 2-Chlorobenzaldehyde appeared as white crystalline solid. The IR Spectrum of the compound N-[3-(2-chlorophenyl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one]semicarbazide (**2**) exhibited five strong absorption bands at 3464.15cm^{-1} & 3326.25cm^{-1} , 1658.78cm^{-1} & 1597.06cm^{-1} and 740.67cm^{-1} characteristic of three NH, C=O and C-Cl respectively. In the ^1H NMR spectrum the appearance of peak at δ 8.946 ppm was due to NH_2 . The nine aromatic protons ($\text{C}_2\text{-H}$, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}$, $\text{C}_4\text{-H}$, $\text{C}_5\text{-H}$, $\text{C}_6\text{-H}$, $\text{C}_3'\text{-H}$, $\text{C}_4'\text{-H}$, $\text{C}_5'\text{-H}$, $\text{C}_6'\text{-H}$) appeared as a multiplet in the δ (7.364-8.321 ppm). C_2 aliphatic protons appeared as a doublet at δ 6.583 ppm and C_3

aliphatic protons appeared as a multiplet at δ 2.564-2.569 ppm. The mass spectrum showed the molecular ion peak at m/z (317). Elemental analysis provided the carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen composition which agreed with the calculated value. Thus the molecular formula of (1) is $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{ClN}_3\text{O}_2$. On the basis of above spectral details the structure of the compound established as N-[3-(2-chlorophenyl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one]semicarbazide (**2**).

N-[3-(2-chlorophenyl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one]semicarbazide(**2**)

ANTIBACTERIALACTIVITY

The samples (1) and (2) were tested by the well diffusion method. Different concentration of the extracts (100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was prepared by reconstituting with methanol. The test microorganisms were seeded into respective medium by spread plate method 10 μl (10cells/ml) with the 24h cultures of bacteria growth in nutrient broth. After solidification the filter paper wells (5mm in diameter) impregnated with the extracts were placed on test organism-seeded plates. Tetracycline (100 μg) used as standard for

antibacterial test. The antibacterial assay plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hrs. The diameters of the inhibition zones were measured in mm (**Table.1** and **Table.2**).

Table.1: Antibacterial study of N-[3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one]thiourea (1)

Compound	Concentration	Zone of inhibition (mm)	
		E. Coli	Klebsiella pneumoniae
N-[3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one]thiourea (1)	10µg	-	1.0
	20µg	2.5	2.2
	30µg	-	1.2
Standard (Tetracycline)	100µg	4.5	4.0

Table.2 : Antibacterial study of N-[3-(2-chlorophenyl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one]semicarbazide (2)

Compound	Concentration	Zone of inhibition (mm)	
		E. Coli	Klebsiella pneumoniae
N-[3-(2-chlorophenyl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one]semicarbazide (2)	10µg	2.0	1.0
	20µg	1.8	1.0
	30µg	1.3	4.2
Standard (Tetracycline)	100µg	4.5	4.0

CONCLUSION

We have reported N-[3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one]thiourea (**1**) and N-[3-(2-chlorophenyl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one]semicarbazide (**2**) through three component condensation reaction consisting of active hydrogen containing compounds. The different functional groups were confirmed by satisfactory vibrational band assignment from FT-IR spectrum. The content and molecular structure of compound is determined through ¹H-NMR and spectrum. The antibacterial studies were also taken for each compound. In the antibacterial studies; N-[3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one]thiourea (**1**) shows higher activity in lower concentration (20µg) against E. Coli and N-[3-(2-chlorophenyl)-1-phenylpropan-1-one]semicarbazide (**2**) shows higher activity in lower concentration (30µg) against Klebsiella pneumonia. Further, this technique offers a widespread application in the area of drug discovery, combinatorial and medicinal chemistry preparation.

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